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TOPIC N° 1 – METHODS, TOOLS AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR SSB D PURPOSES

ZETA PREDICT: AN ENALOS CLOUD PLATFORM TOOLBOX FOR THE ZETA POTENTIAL CALCULATION OF COATED SPHERICAL NANOPARTICLES BASED ON SEM/TEM IMAGES, DLVO THEORY AND ATOMIC FORCE FIELDS

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Zeta (ζ) potential is a widely used metric to describe the stability of colloidal dispersions. Zeta potential is the value of the electric potential at the slipping plane (e.g. at the distance of a Debye length from the surface which is considered to be the thickness of the double layer). Several experimental techniques are used to calculate the zeta potential (e.g. electrophoresis, streaming potential, colloid vibration current etc.). The Zeta-Predict toolbox powered by Enalos Cloud Platform suggests an alternative method for the zeta potential calculation based on SEM/TEM images of colloidal dispersions, the DLVO theory, and atomistic force-fields. In this method, special treatment has been applied for the van der Waals interactions by applying the Hamaker equations for coated spherical nanoparticles. The method is limited to colloidal dispersions that experience coagulation after large time intervals where the colloidal particle distances remain unchanged. The equilibrium distance among these colloidal particles is calculated using SEM images imported through the Zeta-Predict Toolbox by the user. Zeta-Predict toolbox provides the option to users to calculate the particle radius (core and shell) and the interparticle distance by selecting points in the SEM image using their computer mouse. Moreover, users insert as input the temperature, the dielectric constant of the solvent, the chemical formulas, and the densities of the nanoparticle (core and shell) and the solvent. In addition, the concentration, and the valence of the anions/cations inside the solvent are selected too. After running the Zeta-Predict toolbox, the zeta-potential, the surface electric potential and the surface charge density are calculated and provided as output at the bottom of the Graphical User Interface.

Figure 1. ζ -predict Graphical User Interface

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TOPIC 1

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